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Structuring Determinants on Learners’ Academic Performance in The New Normal

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Abstract: This research was designed to assess the identified determinants on learner’s performance that helps them improve their learning experiences under the new normal. The descriptive correlational method was employed using survey questionnaire. There were 65 respondents who were participated using purposive sampling. The data were statistically analyzed through percentage, frequency count, weighted mean, ranking and chi-square test utilizing 0.05 level of significance. Findings showed that motivation, learning environment, academic and parental support contributes to the overall academic performance of the students, however, it was rated as moderately agree which denotes a moderate influence. While technological support perceived as the less determinant. By recognizing the impact of this results, it is very important to provide appropriate support to the learners. Thus, the results suggested that there is still a need to elevate the support of the teachers and parents to provide quality learning. It can also be observed that despite covid-19 pandemic and new set-up of education, learners were still motivated to acquired quality learning.

Keywords: Determinants, Academic performance, New normal setting

1. Introduction

As the globe gets more linked, the risks we face increase proportionately (Manuj & Mentzer, 2008; Currie & Oheigeartaigh, 2018). The COVID-19 epidemic has afflicted people regardless of their nationality, degree of education, income, or gender (Suresh & Rani, 2021; Firang, 2020). However, the same cannot be said of its repercussions, which have disproportionately harmed the most disadvantaged (Schleicher, 2020). As of March 2020, COVID-19 has developed into a worldwide epidemic, causing havoc throughout the globe and putting the world to a halt (WHO, 2020). As a result, the authorities have implemented a variety of social and physical distancing measures, including the closure of non-essential companies, the closure of schools and colleges, and the prohibition of travel, cultural and athletic events, as well as social gatherings (UNPB, 2020; Parnel et al., 2020).

Additionally, the COVID-19 epidemic has wreaked havoc on education systems worldwide, affecting almost 1.6 billion students in more than 190 nations across all continents (Stanistreet et al., 2020; Paudel, 2021; Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021). School and other learning facility closures have touched 94% of the world's student population, rising to 99 percent in low- and lower-middle-income nations (UN, 2020).

Similarly, Burgess et al. (2020) asserted that the COVID-19 pandemic is primarily a health emergency. The problem exemplifies the challenge that politicians face in deciding whether to close or keep schools running. Bozkurt et al., (2020) Ali & Kaur (2020) emphasized that numerous families worldwide are experiencing serious short-term disruption as a result of home schooling; it has a profound effect on not only parents' productivity, but also on children's social lives and learning. On an unprecedented and untested scale, education is migrating online. Additionally, student exams are migrating online, resulting in a great deal of trial and error and uncertainty for everyone (Burgess & Sievertsen, 2020; Toquero et al., 2021). Numerous evaluations have been canceled outright. Notably, these disruptions will not be a one-off occurrence; they will likely have long-term effects for the afflicted cohorts and will likely exacerbate inequality.

Moreover, UNESCO (2020) stated that these nationwide closures are impacting hundreds of millions of students. Several other countries have implemented localized closures impacting millions of additional learners. UNESCO is supporting countries in their efforts to mitigate the immediate impact of school closures, particularly for more vulnerable and disadvantaged communities, and to facilitate the continuity of education for all through remote learning. Similarly, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2020) indicated that school closures due to the COVID-19 outbreak have disrupted the education of at least 290.5 million students worldwide, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (as cited by McCarty (2020).

In the Philippines, the Covid-19 crisis has affected about 27 million learners, 1 million teachers and non-teaching staff, as well as the families of learners. The Department of Education (DepEd) recently announced that classes for the next school year would begin on October 5, 2020. Classes may start earlier, but there will be no physical return to school (Obama, 2020). A lot of buzzwords have come up ever since schools started adopting alternative modes of learning. Among these terms include online learning, blended learning, modular, flexible remote learning and distance learning. While home school and online learning are among the proposed solutions, access to technology and the internet, especially in remote areas, remains a challenge. In the public education system, it is not uncommon for students to lack internet connection at home or be unable to afford to “load” their phones regularly. Some do not even have computers or phones at all. As this is a reality that many schools, students, and communities will face, the DepEd proposes a combination of different learning modalities and will be using the Blended Learning approach (Jorge, 2020).

However, due to a problem of internet connection and lack of technological resources, majority of the students and parents prepare printed modules or modular distance learning instead of online learning. DepEd (2020) stated that printed modules or modular distance learning is a learning delivery mode where interaction takes place between the teacher and the students who are geographically remote from each other

during instruction. This means lessons will be delivered outside the traditional face-to-face setup. According to Llego (2020) modular distance learning involves individualized instruction that allows learners to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, whichever is applicable in the context of the learner, and other learning resources like Learner's Materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides and other study materials. In addition, president Duterte himself has said that he won't be allow students to go back to school until it is safe or a vaccine becomes available, hence schools are directed to implement a learning modality where lessons will be delivered to the students in their homes (Uy, 2020).

Most earlier studies by Zaheer and Munir (2020) distance learning improves the access to education for all the aspiring students and it also overcomes the issues and concerns especially in this time of pandemic. Like conventional system, DL is also not free from certain shortcomings, for example, burden of learning is shifted on the learner (though flexibility is there), there is too much diversity in the same course, more importantly student and teacher are separated and there is a lack of guidance on the parts of the students. In addition, Au et al. (2018) noted that to enhance student persistence, teachers should be appointed for proper guidance of students for better learning. Similarly, Tinga (2020) emphasized that one of the incalculable losses of the Covid-19 pandemic is in how children and teenagers have, in many ways, been force to "grow up." In particular, due to the shift to online and modular learning, students are now taking more of an initiative in their own education and learning process. Hence, students and teachers are entering an unprecedented time of distance learning experience its own unique challenges.

One way of recovering from this problem could be better understand the determinants of academic performance in distance learning education in this time of pandemic to promote quality education. Jorge (2020) stated that the new normal in education simply relies on the current resources and theories in education that support students learning. Such factors such as home environment (conduciveness to learning), learner attitudes toward home learning (motivation), technology competence can affect learner outcomes (technological supports), academic support, parent participation and support. Based on the recent findings and literature review, there is a large gap of literature or less studies that focuses on the determinants of academic performance in times of pandemic. The intent in conducting this research is to develop and increased understanding of student perceptions of the identified determinants that contributes to their academic performance in terms motivation, home environment, academic supports, parental supports and technological resources that helps students in their learning.

1. Purpose of the Study

This research assessed the determinants of learners' academic performance in the new normal. Learner's profile and determinants were analyzed and treated to assessed if there's a relationship between the variables.

2. Research Methodology

The descriptive correlational method was employed using survey questionnaire. The research environment was the selected school in the province of Cebu. The group

respondents of the study were the learners in the identified schools typically from grade level 5 to 6. The respondents were chosen from a target population; hence, purposive sampling was utilized in this study. This questionnaire was adapted from Self-Regulating Capacity in Vocabulary Learning' scale (2014). The instruments analyze the motivation of the students to learn independently. For the learning environment, this questionnaire was adapted from Lyons et al. (2018) the instruments include ideal learning environment in learning and the remaining questionnaire were researcher made. While the 24-item scale the learners' response the items by selecting "Strongly Agree", "Agree", "Moderately Agree", "Disagree", "Strongly Disagree".

3. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Motivation

Motivation	Mean	VD
Home education makes me more motivated to learn	3.37	MA
I am sure I can do an excellent job on the problems and tasks assigned	2.77	MA
I'm certain I can understand the ideas taught in this course	2.69	MA
During the process of learning, I feel satisfied with my performance	2.83	MA
I often find that I have been reading a lesson, but ended up knowing less about it	2.99	MA
When I feel stressed about learning, I simply want to give up	2.69	MA
Weighted Mean	2.89	MA

Table 1 reflects the motivation of the students in terms of studying in the new normal of education. Data shows that the statement home education makes me more motivated to learn got the highest weighted mean of 3.37 which verbally described as moderately agree. On the other hand, the statement I'm certain I can understand the ideas taught in this course got the lowest weighted mean of 2.69 which verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that the students have easily adopt the new setting in acquiring quality education in the new normal however, they were uncertain if they can acquire the education that they need to possessed. According to recent Adec Innovations (2020) studies, certain modalities of learning are done without the presence of an instructor or facilitator, and students may get confused about how to go through the course, particularly if they are unaware of the expected or intended outcome. At times, pupils may require the constant supervision of their lecturers via virtual methods.

According to Kennedy (2020), the COVID-19 epidemic took a heavy toll on everyone, yet although working from home is possible, teaching and learning may be rather difficult. Getting out of bed is a hassle in and of itself, even more so when you know you will be spending the day at your work desk. Not to mention the numerous diversions available both offline and online. Street sirens, spouse and siblings in adjacent rooms, and gadget reminders to respond to email or social media messages. In an online learning environment, motivating learners to participate and learn more effectively is critical. Regardless of the format or manner of delivery, using these concepts can assist your kids in learning more effectively, faster, and more efficiently during this challenging moment. This implies that because students are pushed to continue their education from their homes, they confront an altogether new set of

distractions that may prevent them from finishing the essential courses, demonstrating the critical importance of desire to accomplish a task.

Table 2. Learning Environment

Learning Environment	Mean	VD
There are sufficient resources available at home to supports my study	2.79	MA
My learning environment contributes the way I learn	3.02	MA
My learning environment at home is comfortable for learning	2.75	MA
My learning environment facilitates a safe environment for working a task	2.94	MA
Most of the time I have received academic supports from my friends	2.83	MA
Most of the time I need academic supports to complete a task and activities	2.66	MA
Weighted Mean	2.83	MA

In terms of the learning environment of the students, data shows that the statement refers to my learning environment contributes the way I learn got the highest weighted mean of 3.02, which verbally described as moderately agree. While the statement refers to most of the time, I need academic supports to complete a task and activities got the lowest weighted mean of 2.66 which verbally described as moderately agree. Overall, the learning environment got a weighted mean of 2.83 which verbally described as moderately agree.

For the last three decades, an increasing number of research have established that the home educational environment (HLE) is a significant predictor of academic and social development disparities in children (e.g., most recently, Rose, Lehl, Ebert, & Weinert, 2018; Tamis-LeMonda, Luo, McFadden, Bandel, & Vallotton, 2019). However, the criteria and measurement of what constitutes the HLE vary significantly among research. Participation of children in learning activities, the quality of parent–child relationships, and the availability of learning resources are three critical characteristics of the home learning environment that contribute to students' development growth (Bradley & Corwyn, 2002).

With the development of the home literacy and numeracy models (Sénéchal & LeFevre, 2002; Skwarchuck, Sowinski, & LeFevre, 2014), HLE measurements have grown more precise and established in connection to particular outcome measures (e.g., Manolitsis, Georgiou, & Tziraki, 2013). These novel techniques have aided our knowledge of what occurs in the home setting in terms of learning activities across several teachers perceive of a child's academic development.

However, only a few studies have studied longitudinal changes in the HLE and their long-term impacts on children's outcomes (e.g., Sammons et al., 2015; Son & Morrison, 2010) or have been done from an educational effectiveness research viewpoint. Thus, future educational effectiveness research should focus on the HLE's involvement in greater detail and on how it may interact (perhaps mediate or moderate) with institutional impacts at various levels related to students, school, and instructors. Thus, the home learning environment has an effect on students' academic success.

Table 3. Academic Support

Academic Support	Mean	VD
I have received academic supports from my parents	2.95	MA
I have received academic supports from my siblings	3.15	MA
I have received academic supports from my teachers	3.08	MA
I have received academic supports from an internet source	2.95	MA
I have received academic supports from my friends	2.62	MA
I need academic supports to complete a task and activities	2.68	MA
Weighted Mean	2.91	MA

Table 3 reflects the academic supports that student received in the new normal of education. Data shows that the statement refers to most of the time I have received academic supports from my siblings got the highest weighted mean of 3.15 which verbally described as moderately agree. While, the statement refers to most of the time I have received academic supports from my friends got the lowest weighted mean of 2.62 which verbally described as moderately agree. Overall, academic support got an overall weighted mean of 2.91 which verbally described as moderately agree. According to Pope (2020), because the 2020 distant learning research project disrupted traditional school schedules and approaches to teaching and learning, teachers now have an opportunity to leverage key lessons and insights gained during this time period to create a new normal that supports effective student well-being, equity, and engagement with learning for all students during the upcoming semester and beyond.

Additionally, it is evident that instructors must give help to kids who may be struggling to adjust to the new normal of schooling. Thus, continual monitoring and follow-up on students' performance is important to the achievement of this new educational paradigm.

Table 4. Parental Support

Parental Support	Mean	VD
My parents helped me develop a good study habit	2.82	MA
My parents motivate me to strive hard and continue to learn independently	3.07	MA
My parents encouraged me to get good grades.	2.38	MA
My parents were strict when it came to completing the module.	2.92	MA
My parents always check to see if I had completed the task and activities in the module	2.78	MA
My parents always checked if I had my breakfast, lunch and dinner.	2.95	MA
Weighted Mean	2.82	MA

Table 4 reflects the parental supports that student received in the new normal of education. Data shows that the statement refers to my parents motivate me to strive hard and continue to learn independently got the highest weighted mean of 3.07 which verbally described as moderately agree. While, the statement refers to my parents encouraged me to get good grades got the lowest weighted mean of 2.32 which verbally described as moderately agree. Overall, parental support got an overall weighted mean of 2.82 which verbally described as moderately agree. According to Malipot (2020), as

students prepare for a "new normal" in education as a result of the COVID-19 crisis-related changes, the Department of Education (DepEd) emphasizes the critical role of parents and guardians in ensuring that their children's learning continues despite anticipated disruptions. Thus, parental participation and support will be critical as the whole elementary system of education prepares for the so-called "new normal". Additionally, Arias (2020) remarked that because this is a novel situation for everyone, particularly parents, who would play a significant role in the new normal setting. Learning will be shifted to kids' homes, with parents taking on some of the duties of instructors. Numerous concerns have been expressed as a result of these developments, including what type of education would be provided at home, how parents will manage their children's learning, particularly toddlers, and what class schedule will full-time be working parents adhere to. As a result, this demonstrates that the critical role of parents in this new normal has a significant impact on adolescents' academic achievement.

Table 5. Technological Support

Technological Support	Mean	VD
I get more actively involved in courses when I use technology to supports my learning	2.4	D
Technology makes my study easier and faster	2.53	D
It motivates me to explore many topics I may not have seen before.	2.52	D
It helps me understand the subject material more deeply	2.87	MA
It makes completing work in my subjects more convenient.	2.77	MA
It allows me to collaborate with others easily, both on and outside of the home premises.	2.38	D
Weighted Mean	2.58	D

Table 5 reflects the role of technological supports that student received in the new normal of education. Data shows that the statement refers to it helps me understand the subject material more deeply got the highest weighted mean of 2.87 which verbally described as moderately agree. While, the statement refers to It allows me to collaborate with others easily, both on and outside of the home premises got the lowest weighted mean of 2.38 which verbally described as Disagree. Overall, technological support got an overall weighted mean of 2.58 which verbally described as disagree. Recent studies by Thedish (2020) stressed the need of educational technology as an immediate topic of focus (EdTech). EdTech has embodied the promise of a much more effective and equitable educational experience for decades. This promise continues to resonate with many, especially those seeking to "reimagine education" via the lens of technology. However, considerable obstacles remain in the way of technology providing more egalitarian learning settings, not fewer. Additionally, because students at the university of the People (2020) engage with technology off-campus, integrating these tools into classroom can help the learning process significantly. Technology simplifies instructors' responsibilities by offering excellent methods for establishing rapport between teacher and student. Additionally, Jakimowicz (2020) emphasized that technology is critical to this new normal, as it will alter workplace standards, both remotely and on the working site. Today, more individuals work remotely than at any point in history, and the majority of them desire to continue working in a hybrid model of remote and in-person employment. As a result, we must partner with educators and leaders, researchers, students and families, and researchers of quality education to develop increasingly equitable and resilient learning systems using technology.

Table 6. Significant Relationship

Pearson $r = 0.3152$		Coef of Determination = 9.94%		
Standard Error = 0.8167				
<i>Determinants VS</i>	<i>Individual r</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P- value</i>
Age	0.0024	0.0344	0.0189	0.9850
Gender	0.0282	0.1090	0.2237	0.8237
Grade Level	-0.0304	0.0162	0.2416	0.8099
Parents Educational Attainment	0.2360	0.0674	1.9280	0.0584
Parents Occupation	0.3062	0.1396	2.5531	0.0131

It can be seen in Table 6 in which the relationship was tested using chi-square at 0.5 at 0.05 level of confidence. With the coefficient of determination of 9.94% and a p-value of higher to 0.05 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05 (0.09850, 0.8237, 0.08099, 0.0584 > 0.05), hence the null hypothesis was not rejected. However, a weak correlation exists on parents' occupation and identified determinants $p > .05$ are statistically significant predictor of academic performance of the students. This was supported by Odoh et al. (2017) result shows that parental occupational level significantly influenced students' academic performance. Moreover, in the study of Sibanda, et al. (2016) showed that the general performance of students has mainly been affected by factors such as lack of resources, discipline and poor morale, problems concerning the implementation policies, and inadequate parental involvement.

4. Conclusion

This study was conducted to assessed the determinants of learners' academic performance in the new normal. Based on the data analysis, it was indicated that motivation, learning environment, academic and parental support do not contribute to the overall academic performance of the students, however, it was rated as moderately agree which denotes a moderate influence. While technological support perceived as the less determinant. By recognizing the impact of this results, it is very important to provide appropriate support to the learners. Moreover, the results of the study denote that despite covid-19 pandemic and new set-up of education, learners were still motivated to learn.

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